

RM ROADMAP

Consensus Document for Country Community PORTUGAL

Co-Creation Session 3: Career Development Framework

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RM ROADMAP

**“Creating Framework Conditions for Research Management to Strengthen
the European Research Area”**

Funded by the European Union’s Horizon Europe Programme

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Framework**

Co-Creation Session 3

Career Development Framework

Contents

1. Introduction	4
2. Summary of Co-Creation Session 3	6
3. Discussion Outcomes of Co-Creation Session 3	8
4. References	27

1. Introduction

This is an important moment for the research management (RM) community in Europe. The European Commission (EC) and countries across Europe want to better understand the current research management landscape to further strengthen the European Research Area (ERA).

Research management includes a broad range of professionals supporting researchers to achieve excellence in research. For the purpose of this co-creation exercise, Research Managers (RMs) are to be considered as broad as possible including: research policy advisers, research managers, financial support staff, data stewards, research infrastructure operators, knowledge transfer officers, business developers, knowledge brokers, innovation managers, etc. For simplicity, we use the term research management but this exercise covers also other terms such as research support, research management and administration, professionals at the interface of science and other terms which are used as the norm in the national landscapes across Europe.

The RM Roadmap Knowledge and Community Platform (KCP) brings research managers together to shape the future of the profession and support the strengthening of an inclusive research management community in Europe. The KCP is a place where research managers share their views and introduce issues for discussion in a solution-focused endeavour. RM Roadmap Ambassadors lead the discussions for each country on the Knowledge and Community Platform, supported by national and regional RM networks.

This co-creation exercise is the biggest collaboration between RM networks ever to take place in Europe. With a focus on learning insights from RMs, the co-creation exercise seeks to establish a robust framework that can support professional growth and collaboration across the EU and associated countries.

By 2023, 40 country communities have been established within the RM Roadmap Ambassador Network. These have been complemented by 10 thematic communities, including 35 additional Ambassadors on top of the 114 national Ambassadors at the beginning of 2024. The RM Roadmap project will use the outcomes from this co-creation exercise to make a roadmap for the future of research

management in Europe and to build and exchange solid knowledge on career framework opportunities, upskilling and networking for research managers. RM Roadmap will ultimately build a value proposition for policy makers and institutional leaders who want to strengthen and modernise their research support departments.

This **consensus document for Country Community PORTUGAL** contains the outcomes of the **Third Co-Creation Session – Career Development Framework**

A short summary of the main outcomes from the co-creation exercise is included in section 2. More information about the topic of career development framework is detailed in section 3.

For more information about the RM Roadmap initiative, the reader can consult the following website:
www.rmroadmap.eu

2. Summary of Co-Creation Session 3

The Portuguese 3rd co-creation session of the RM Roadmap project took place between November 14th 2024 and January 19th 2025 and was the last co-creation exercise to gather feedback on RMs **Career Development Framework and possible funding schemes tailored to RMs**.

The 3rd co-creation session was launched by the project on the platform and, following the session's launch, the Portuguese Ambassadors devised an online form mirroring the EARMA RM Roadmap 3rd co-creation session to solicit feedback from the national community, as this strategy proved successful during the 2nd co-creation session. This form was disseminated via various channels, including the national RM network ("Plataforma de Interface à Ciência", PIC) mailing list - encompassing over 800 Research Managers, personalized emails, LinkedIn, and Facebook, to inform and mobilize the Portuguese community for active participation.

RM-ROADMAP 3rd co-creation session – Career Development Framework - PORTUGAL

The 3rd ROADMAP co-creation session focusses on the following relevant topics:

- Potential training schemes designed to enhance the professional development of Research Manager
- Professional development and career path: the establishment of a competence framework.

The session aims to gather feedback and validation from the national and thematic communities with two aims: first, to identify any potential gaps or missing aspects, second, to gather evidence about any national circumstances that may be relevant when applying the results at the national levels.

The Portuguese (Co)Ambassadors: Tatiana Costa, Luís Silva, Cláudia Barbosa, Mariana Santa-Marta.

For any questions regarding the survey or data protection, please contact Cláudia Barbosa (cbarbosa@av.it.pt).

Seguinte

Concurrently, and in collaboration with PIC, the Portuguese Ambassadors organized a *'Café com Ciência'* event - an online community gathering event hosted by PIC. This event was held on January 17th 2025 where the Ambassadors briefly introduced the RM Roadmap project; shared insights from the 1st and 2nd co-creation session; and engaged with attendees on the evolving outcomes of the ongoing 3rd co-creation session to solidify community perspectives through live feedback and comments.

The event once again received positive feedback from the attendees – around 30 attendees-, indicating a successful outreach and collaborative engagement approach.

No replies were found on the platform for the RM Portuguese community. Using the described approach and strategy, the Ambassadors collected 37 replies through the online form and detailed feedback before RMs at the “Café com Ciência” online event and 8 more replies after the new dissemination and engagement calls (totalling 45 replies).

3. Discussion Outcomes of Co-Creation Session 3

Recommended funded schemes at the EU level

One of the key objectives of the RM-Roadmap project is to recommend an **EU-wide training scheme designed to enhance the professional development of Research Managers**. To ensure that the recommendations are relevant and grounded in the needs of the RM community, we are presenting two potential training schemes for consideration. They have been adapted from well-established researcher-focused programmes, thus ensuring familiarity and ease of adoption by the RM community and policymakers. The proposed schemes for EU-level funding are as follows:

Scheme A - This initiative focuses on supporting the entrance and development of individual RM careers across Europe by providing long-term financial support for individual grants for upskilling through training and mobility. Like the [MSCA Postdoctoral Fellowships](#) and [ERA fellowships](#), Scheme A would offer individual grants, providing flexibility for personal career development without requiring institutional commitments.

Scheme B - This initiative aims at strengthening Research Management through institutional collaboration. Institutions would apply for funding to support staff exchanges and training opportunities across organisations, following the model of [MSCA Staff Exchanges](#) and [ERA Talents](#). Unlike Scheme A, Scheme B requires a strong institutional commitment, fostering the exchange of knowledge and best practices between organisations and sectors. The focus here is on building institutional capacity while also advancing the professional development of RMs involved in these exchanges.

Feedback From PT Community | Training Scheme A

Which features need to be introduced so that this scheme format is feasible and attractive to research managers?

The Portuguese RMs community has diverse views on the design and impact of RM training A Type of schemes, particularly regarding eligibility, institutional support, career development, and mobility requirements. While there is strong support for structured training, concerns exist about practical

implementation and unintended consequences. The only feature that generated a consensus for training scheme A was the type of training, while others were actually revealed as a concern if included in this type of schemes.

Which features need to be introduced so that this scheme format is feasible and attractive to research managers?

Further Key Elements to Include in the Training Scheme:

- Training as a Core Element:** The community agrees that training opportunities such as mentoring, courses, and job shadowing should be the primary focus of the scheme, adapted to the RM career stage and profiles.

Points to consider when designing this training schemes:

- Support for Employer Institutions:** Many institutions struggle with staff shortages, making it difficult to release employees for training. Support mechanisms for these institutions should be considered.

- **Work-Family Balance:** Long-term mobility schemes (e.g., two-year MSCA-PF) may not be suitable for RMs with family commitments. Shorter stays (e.g., one-month programs) could be an alternative, and policies on return from parenthood should be considered.
- **Maternity and Paternity Challenges:** Women, in particular, may face additional obstacles when traveling abroad for training. Family-friendly policies should be incorporated into the scheme.
- **Exclusive Focus on RMs:** The scheme should be designed exclusively for RM professionals, excluding researchers and PIs who also engage in management tasks.

What are the expected impacts of this initiative on the professional development of the RM community?

The Portuguese community was unanimous on the importance of providing paid training opportunities through mobility schemes to RMs (all career stages). We collected several individual comments that reinforced that the major impacts to the RM community and institutions employing RMs would be:

- **Exchange of knowledge and Best Practices:** learning from others, from different settings and environments, and exchanging best practices is essential to capitalize the RMA profession and bring added value to one's institution of origin.
- **Recognition and Formalization of RM Roles as a critical component of the research ecosystem:** Standardizing/harmonizing competencies and training experiences will contribute to greater institutional recognition of the RM profession, paving the way for structured career pathways.
- **Faster Career Progression:** By offering structured training and networking opportunities, the scheme will enable newcomers to the RMs profession and RMs to gain the necessary skills for career advancement, leading to promotions and leadership roles within institutions.
- **Diversification of Career Paths:** Exposure to different research management environments will help professionals explore various RM roles, increasing their employability across institutions and sectors.

- **Enhanced Professional Network:** Cross-border mobility and collaboration will allow RMs to establish international connections, facilitating knowledge-sharing and best practices that benefit both individuals and their institutions.
- **Increased Job Security:** With improved training and recognition, RMs will be better positioned to negotiate career advancements and secure stable, long-term employment within research institutions.
- **Focus on the opportunity for career development:** opportunity to evaluate the potential of career progression (upskilling) by engaging in a specifically designed RMs program and supervisor/mentor and host institution (similarly to the MSCA-PF and ERA fellowships).

Potential Risks:

- Unequal access to opportunities, particularly for mid-career or senior career professionals with no certified trainings professionals with family obligations.
- Risk of precarious employment conditions if institutions do not commit to retaining trained RMs.

How do you rate this initiative in terms of priority?

The majority of the respondents considers the implementation of this initiative to be of a high or very high priority.

How do you rate this initiative in terms of priority?

The RM training scheme A has strong potential to enhance professional development, career progression, and institutional recognition of RMs. However, careful design is needed to address concerns about career-stage restrictions, mobility challenges, institutional support, and family-friendly policies. A flexible and inclusive approach will be key to ensuring the scheme benefits the entire RM community.

Feedback From PT Community | Training Scheme B

Which features need to be introduced so that this scheme format is feasible and attractive to research managers?

In what concerns training scheme B, the most important feature highlighted by the Portuguese RMs community is the type of course (mentoring, courses, job shadowing) which is the single element for which more than 50% positive answers were received.

Three features (career stage, return guarantee and institutional commitment) are considered less relevant, and the least relevant defining feature appears to be the type of institution, with a positive answer by less than a third (n=14) of all respondents (n=45).

Which features need to be introduced so that this scheme format is feasible and attractive to research managers?

As to additional features or characteristics that should be considered, while only 1 respondent indicated a relevance of further factors, a total of 5 suggestions were made, highlighting that such a scheme should:

- give opportunities to personnel with term or partial contracts;
- not try to replicate ongoing funding schemes;
- as such, be tailor-made for the RM community;
- need awareness from the institutions;
- and be limited to RMs only.

What are the expected impacts of this initiative on the professional development of the RM community?

The expected impacts of such an initiative in the RM community are manifold, with respondents highlighting that it would allow:

- an **improved professional valorization and career recognition**;
- **opportunities for networking and community building**;
- **alignment with research** goals;
- **career progression**;
- and, in detail, it is considered that this scheme would **foster capacity building** at several levels:
 - ***individually*** – leading to an improved knowledge and sharing of best practices on RM common or/and shared ground;
 - and ***institutionally***
 - as RMs require institutional experience - more so than scientists - such a mobility scheme, designed with the support of the institution are considered ideal;

- being tailored to the institution, such a scheme would require that each institution firstly reflects on its challenges/needs and only subsequently designs a project to fill the found gaps;
- it would constitute a step forward on promoting the professional stability of the RM community but also to help enhance the competitiveness of each institution by forming the required foundations in terms of staff expertise and knowledge;
- it would prove to be very helpful to further research management capabilities within institutions, allowing a more effective onboarding of new colleagues, especially those new to the profession.

While considering the defining characteristics of scheme B, it was highlighted by the community that while this scheme has some potential advantages over scheme A, it also has some potential limitations.

Potential advantages:

- Scheme B appears to be a **more inclusive initiative** as the merit of the institution – rather than the individual - would be the only one being evaluated. Many of the RMs need capacitation in applications and therefore, in an individual application they would be doubly harmed.
- this **scheme can highlight the importance of the RM role and the establishment of scientific PMOs** within institutions: these offices would oversee project and research management comprehensively, rather than focusing solely on financial management (often the primary emphasis in many institutions).

Potential limitations:

- Because this scheme involves an **institutional commitment**, it can be **more difficult** to implement.

- The heavy reliance on organizational commitment **may disproportionately benefit well-resourced institutions**, leaving those with fewer capabilities struggling to participate effectively.
- These actions are more limiting to the knowledge of what it entails and often **end up being an extra task rather than incorporated into daily routines**.
- There is a risk of short-term outcomes if **institutional commitment wanes after initial exchanges**.
- A significant strength is its potential to offer opportunities to personnel with fixed-term/part-time contracts: however, ensuring equal access requires targeted policies to mitigate institutional biases that might prioritize permanent staff. **Institutions often prioritize individuals with longer tenure**, offering them more opportunities to participate in training and events. While this approach recognizes their experience and loyalty, **it can inadvertently limit access for newer or temporary staff, who may equally benefit from these opportunities**.

The Portuguese community also added two reflections that rather than being classified as negative / positive should be taken into consideration when drafting similar training schemes:

- one respondent highlights that MSCA Staff Exchanges, COST and ERA Talents already consider administrative staff as eligible staff, thus RMs are somehow considered. Doubts remain on what would the differences between such a scheme as the one advertised be, as well as the expected impacts of this initiative on the professional development of the RM community, when compared to the existing broader schemes (thus reinforcing the previously highlighted point that such a scheme should be tailored specifically to RMs);
- while a further respondent considered that it is crucial that institutions recognize RM professionals as an important part of the scientific community, and institutional awareness and commitment is a very important part of this process.

How do you rate this initiative in terms of priority?

The majority of the respondents considers the implementation of this initiative to be of a high or very high priority, as can be seen in the following graph.

How do you rate this initiative in terms of priority?

Similarly to scheme A, training scheme B also shows strong potential to enhance professional development, career progression, and institutional recognition of RMs, but also institutional capacitation as it has the potential to positively impact a wider group of RMs within the institution and effect relevant institutional changes. However, institutional support is paramount to this approach and needs to be sustained in order for this scheme to be successful.

Professional Development and Career Path

The Competence Framework for Research Managers initiated by CARDEA has been adjusted with the inputs from RM ROADMAP. The current version of the possible European Competence Framework for Research Managers (RM Comp) is being finalised and validated with stakeholders, including policy-makers, RPO leaders and Research Managers under the coordination of Action 17, the Research Management Initiative.

RM Comp aims to facilitate professional development by offering clear learning outcomes and progression models, encouraging Research Managers to enhance their skills and competences. The framework aims to standardize RM competencies, support career planning, and promote the recognition and value of RM roles across Europe.

Given the fluid and flexible nature of the profession, with constantly emerging roles and fields, the RM Comp also underlines several key aspects: entry into the profession can occur at various levels based on educational background and expertise; professional development should be possible both vertically and across specializations; leadership in research support services should be recognized as a specialized expertise, while leadership skills should be acknowledged across all competency areas; and RM Comp should remain a dynamic document that evolves with the profession.

Accordingly, the European Competence Framework for Research Manager defines 9 competence areas, 53 competences and 843 learning outcomes along 4 proficiency levels (foundational, intermediate, advanced, expert).

The inputs from RM ROADMAP includes the elaboration of the definition of research management, adding one additional competence area (soft skills/personal attributes) and the inclusion of several subject matter expertise, including Research Infrastructure Management; Research Ethics and Integrity; Research, Strategy and Policy Development; and Research Support Service Delivery, as well, as the separation of Pre-award and Post-award, and the related learning outcomes.

Q3.1: Once a Europe-wide professional development framework and career path is formulated, what actions would be necessary for the adoption or adaptation of this framework and career path for Research Managers to your national/ thematic community?

In spite of not all respondents answering this question (17 answers to the online form, plus live participation at the *Café com Ciência*), the feedback from the community was quite homogeneous and the majority of the survey takers pointed out relevant aspects such as the need for **policy alignment, stakeholder engagement, institutional commitment, training, career recognition, and evaluation mechanisms** to successfully implement the framework.

More specifically, the following aspects and actions were suggested:

1. Alignment with National Policies and Official Recognition

- Ensure that the framework aligns with **national research policies** and funding mechanisms (e.g., FCT in Portugal).
- Advocate for **government recognition** of Research Management (RM) as a formal career path with clear progression.
- Engage key policymakers and **stakeholders with experience in RM** to highlight the urgency of recognizing and structuring the profession.

2. Engagement with Key Stakeholders

- Establish a **working group** with representatives from universities, research centers, government bodies, and RM associations.
- Consult with **current RM professionals** to help institutions and individuals define competencies within the new framework.
- Ensure employers of RMs understand the framework and assess whether a **new professional category** is needed or if it can be integrated into existing structures.

3. Institutional Commitment and Support Structures

- Encourage universities and research centers to **develop internal RM career policies** aligned with the European framework.
- Strengthen **national RM networks** to facilitate adoption and provide ongoing guidance.
- Organize training programs, workshops, and information sessions to familiarize institutions and RMs with the framework.

4. Training, Professional Development and Dedicated Funding

- Implement **targeted training programs** to equip RMs with skills relevant to local needs.
- Secure **dedicated funding** for RM training and skill development.
- Provide **resources and tools** to support career progression within the framework.

5. Recognition and Career Path Distinction

- Ensure RMs are recognized as a **specialized profession** distinct from administrative and technical staff.
- Raise awareness among **researchers, administrators, and policymakers** about the value of RM and its impact on institutional competitiveness and efficiency.
- Highlight the benefits of adopting a standardized framework, including **enhanced career prospects, institutional productivity, and increased competitiveness**.

6. Monitoring, Evaluation and Continuous Improvement

- Establish **evaluation mechanisms** to measure the effectiveness of the framework and identify areas for improvement.
- Promote **communication between thematic communities** to avoid fragmentation and enhance collaboration.
- Develop a **sustainability plan** that includes long-term funding, partnerships, and institutional commitments, etc.

Examples of participant's feedback include:

- *"Align with National Policies: Ensure compatibility with existing policies and funding mechanisms led by FCT or national entities. Involve Key Actors: Establish a working group with representatives from FCT, universities, research centres, and the RM community. Policy and Strategic Development, National Policy Framework: Work with FCT to integrate the RM career path into national research and innovation strategies. Institutional Strategies: Encourage universities and RC to develop their internal RM career development policies aligned with the Europe-wide framework. Funding Allocation: Secure funding from FCT and EU programs to support professional development initiatives"*
- *"Research Managers and Administrators are technical and administrative staff, with a level of specialization which should be recognized but this cannot be used to bundle researchers who chose a different career path in the same category as administrative and technical staff."*
- *"It would be really important to ensure that the institutions commit themselves with this framework (maybe sign a document with mandatory milestones to be accomplished?). If this does not happen, only a few of us will benefit from the framework. Another important thing is to ensure that thematic communities communicate between each other. At least in Portugal it is common to find clear cision between many of the communities and all our work would be facilitated if there was more communication!."*
- *"It is needed a restructure of the current national view, FCT needs to understand and respect this career aka the government needs to understand and officially recognize this"*

career state and progression for it to be recognized and applied. I think important stakeholders, that have already a long track record with RM should share statements and help policymakers to understand the urgency of the situation”.

- *“The employers of research managers need to first understand the framework and its aims. Then, they need to check whether the creation of a new profession in their institution is mandatory in order to account for the recognition of research management as a profession with appropriate career progression or if it can be suitably incorporated from an already-existing career path. The research managers that they employ should absolutely be consulted in the process.!*
- *“Capacity Building:*
 - *Organize training programs, workshops, and information sessions to familiarize Research Managers and institutions with the new framework.*
 - *Provide resources and tools to support skill development and career progression in line with the framework.*
 - *Dedicate funding dedicated to the training of RM.*
 - *Establish working groups or advisory committees to facilitate discussions and gather input.*
 - *Raise awareness among researchers, administrators, and policymakers about the value of Research Management as a distinct profession.*
 - *Highlight the benefits of adopting a standardized framework, such as enhanced career prospects, improved institutional efficiency, and increased competitiveness.”*

Q3.2 What is needed to make the professional development framework recognised by law or by relevant regulations at country level so that it provides clear career path to research performing organisations when employing RMs overcoming the current situation when RMs are employed under some sub-categories of administrative staff, for instance?

While not all the respondents answered this question (again only 17 answers to the online form, plus live participation at the *Café com Ciência*), the feedback from the community was quite homogeneous

and the majority of the survey takers pointed out relevant aspects such as the need for strong advocacy towards policy and new legislations that recognize the Research Managers Professional identity and career framework to successfully recognize the Research Managers professional development framework by law or by relevant regulations in Portugal at the National level.

1. Advocate for Policy and Regulatory Changes

- Push for **formal recognition of RMs in European and national legislation**, advocating for directives instead of recommendations.
- Draft policy proposals or amendments to existing regulations defining RMs as a distinct category.
- Encourage funding agencies to recognize and require certified RMs in grant applications and project management.

2. Increase Awareness, Establish a Professional Identity and Legal Recognition

- Establish a professional association to advocate for the field and serve as a unified voice.
- Advocate for RMs to be recognized as a distinct profession in national labor laws and employment regulations.
- Create an independent professional category with its own classification code (e.g., CAE in Portugal [1]).
- Promote public recognition of the career at institutional and governmental levels (e.g., inclusion in Tax and Customs Authority records).
- Define clear roles, responsibilities, and competencies to distinguish RMs from administrative or purely financial staff.
- Establish a clear but adaptable framework of RM functions.

3. Develop a Standardized Career Framework

- Define career progression levels (e.g., junior, mid-level, senior RMs) based on qualifications, experience, and performance.

- Integrate career progression into existing national remuneration systems (e.g., *Tabela Remuneratória Única* [2]).
- Ensure RMs are evaluated distinctly from non-specialized administrative staff in HR assessments.
- Support training and competence development programs to enhance the RM profession's credibility

4. Institutional and Political Engagement

- Promote the adoption of RM frameworks in national policies and research organizations.
- Identify national 'champions' to promote the framework within institutions.
- Develop certification systems to validate RM competencies and qualifications.

Examples of participant's feedback include:

- ***"It is very important to have a professional association, that can be the voice of RMAs introducing our profession as a crucial and specialized part of the R&D ecosystem. Recognition is different from having a nationwide career path, and while many professions with established associations may not have such paths, the current number of RMAs may not yet justify one. Our role should be elevated and acknowledged as important and there should be a clear framework for expertise levels, from junior to senior, as well as corresponding remuneration levels within the Tabela Remuneratória Única."***
- ***"A separate independent professional category should be created for research managers with its own code (CAE in Portugal) - this would help self-identification, provide room to grow as a profession and to be heard at a political level and avoid having people in often underpaid admin staff positions performing specialised research management"***
- ***"Establish a clear but adaptable functions performed by an RMA"***
- ***"Advocate for the inclusion of RMs a distinct profession in national labor laws or regulations;"***
- ***"Specific career or within technical careers already recognized"***

- *“It is essential to **advocate for changes at both the European and national levels.** This includes formal recognition of RMs in EU legislation (European Directives instead of Recommendations), **establishing a standardized framework for qualifications and career progression, and integrating these standards into national laws and employment practices.** By creating a distinct classification for RMs, aligning with national education systems, and incentivizing research organizations to adopt these frameworks, the role of RMs can be elevated, providing them with clear, legally supported career pathways.”*
- *“**Change institution HR regulation to recognize RM as a special category with specific salaries and progression rules** (in case it does not exist). It would be also important **to evaluate RM in a distinct way** as non-specialized staff is evaluated. At least in Portugal Universities, we are evaluated based in a few competences and objectives. It would be necessary **for the major national R&D institutions to formally recognize the RM career path and demand legal guidance (laws) to govern these professionals in a respectful and fair way,** and not under general laws that do not apply to the professional's demands.”*
- *“Encourage national funding bodies to require or recommend the involvement of certified RMs in grant applications and project management as a condition for funding.”*
- *“**Publicizing the career at institutional level,** recognizing the existence of the career in the Tax and Customs Authority, and including career progression in the TRU remuneration tables. If necessary, some requirements by funding bodies for the existence of these managers.”*
- *“**Draft policy proposals** or amendments to existing regulations that define RMs as a separate category, distinct from administrative staff, with clear roles and responsibilities; Clearly delineate RM roles, responsibilities, and competencies within the framework, distinguishing them from administrative or purely financial roles;”*
- *“**Develop a structured career path with levels of progression** (e.g., junior, mid-level, senior RMs) linked to qualifications, experience, and performance;”*

Q3.3: Are there any existing initiatives in your country/thematic community that could support the adoption and adaptation? For instance, are there any plans to change legislation related to the recognition of RMs? Or are there any discussions at national level to address the currently missing career framework for RMs? Please elaborate if you are aware of any initiatives.

The Portuguese community was in full agreement that Portugal is still in an early stage of both organizing and recognizing the RM profession:

- **there is no national legislation specifically addressing the career framework for RMs;**
- the absence of a centralized approach results in **fragmented career structures across institutions** (*“an effort has been put in motion to make this change. Namely, some universities have started to create internal guidelines and professional categories that may comprise the RM community in a more adequate manner and consequently help them design a career path within that academic environment. But such changes have been made individually, and there is no common framework being followed (as far as I'm aware)”*).
- and the **visibility of existing local efforts remains a challenge**, as they are not widely recognized beyond individual institutions (*“Universities under the foundation regime had created a job function and a career path for RMs. But these are "local" management decisions not MS decisions therefore with a lack of visibility”*)

But while progress in Portugal may be slower when compared to other countries, **efforts to establish a formal Research Manager career path in Portugal are definitely taking place and may be supported by European-wide initiatives:**

- *“To the best of my knowledge, there are no country-level initiative with this objective. What I think that is important in Portugal is how RM community is organising and make small but steady steps in order to be an Association. Probably we are late in taking this step, but we are doing what is very important”*.
- *“While there is no comprehensive national legislative framework specifically for Research Managers in Portugal, existing initiatives such as the work of PIC (Plataforma de Interface à*

Ciência), the development of internal career frameworks in universities, and ongoing discussions within research bodies like FCT provide a foundation for the recognition and professionalization of RMs. These efforts, combined with the potential influence of a Europe-wide framework, could support the creation of a clearer and more formal career path for RMs in the future”.

At the center of this is **PIC** – Plataforma de Interface à Ciência - the informal network of RMs in Portugal which is **working towards constituting itself as a formal(ized) professional association to support the recognition and valorisation of the RM community** (*“I just know PIC - Plataforma de Interface à Ciência, that is starting to officially move to help in that adoption - although still in the first steps”*).

4. References

[1] Instituto Nacional de Estatística. (n.d.). CAE-Rev.3. Retrieved February 14, 2025, from https://www.ine.pt/xportal/xmain?xpid=INE&xpgid=ine_publicacoes&PUBLICACOESpub_boui=10376048&PUBLICACOESmodo=2

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